

Guideline

Management of skin lesions with the C-Rapid-H-Plus Protocol

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Abstract

Skin cancer, especially malignant melanoma, can vary greatly in appearance and usually develops very quickly. Therefore, the ABCDE rule (also known as the ABCD rule in some countries) was propagated many years ago to help medical laymen to recognize for themselves when it is time to see a dermatologist. But how effective is this rule? Our previous work clearly demonstrates that another self-monitoring protocol has a higher sensitivity and better results than the outdated ABCDE rule: the **C-Rapid-H-Plus Protocol** which has also become an important tool in tele-dermatology.

The C-Rapid-H-Plus Protocol

The **C-Rapid-H-Plus** protocol¹ is proving to be a strategy of significantly improved patient safety in the era of teledermatology. Its establishment and success is inextricably linked to the enabling of telemedicine services in the field of dermatology. Above all, it can also be implemented in traditional dermatological medical practices, provided that a privacy-protected digital "consultation room" is set up and reliably used.

- C** stands for **change** in any way, shape, or form.
- Rapid** means **very prompt excision**, within any hesitation, 10 days at the latest without dermatoscopy or other time consuming tests prior to excision.
- H** is about leaving to make the **definitive diagnosis to a histopathology lab**.
- Plus** expresses the offer and encouragement to send in photos of changing skin lesions together with a detailed message in the interval, i.e. in the long periods **between regular check-ups** in the local practice (at any time, around the clock), which will be evaluated, analyzed and answered by a dermatologist at the latest after 24 hours.

Real world implications

Since the introduction of the C-Rapid-H-Plus protocol in 2020 in the clinics at which we work, we have seen a 58.6% (until February 2022) decrease in advanced stage skin cancer cases at first patient-dermatologist contact.

The number of skin cancer cases requiring non-surgical follow-up after wide and deep excision has dropped to zero in our own patients. This is highly remarkable. We assume that this is also related to the less complex patient education and the digital consultation room as a convenient and always accessible service for patients. The latter in particular seems to be of immense importance.

Conclusion

By replacing the unreliable and often confusing ABCDE rule^{7,8,9} with the C-Rapid-H-Plus protocol, we were able to reduce the number of advanced skin cancer cases in our patients to zero. A result that is consistent with data from other work. Telemedicine will and must play an important role in this new approach, just as the hesitation regarding excision biopsies in dermatology must come to an end.

Conflicts of interest

Dr. Diamandis, Dr. Lazar and Dr. Seideman work in the field of (immuno-)dermatology as clinicians. Dr. Makri and Dr. Ivanova have nothing to declare.

References

1. Tudor, Adrian, Feldman, Jonathan, & Diamandis, Carolina. (2021). Why the ABCDE rule is not helpful but dangerous in skin cancer prevention (3.9). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5731554>
2. Turrisi R, Hultgren B, Mallett KA, Martini M, Robinson JK. Comparison of Efficacy of Differing Partner-Assisted Skin Examination Interventions for Melanoma Patients: A Randomized Clinical Trial. *JAMA Dermatol.* 2015 Sep;151(9):945-51. doi: 10.1001/jamadermatol.2015.0690. PMID: 26049533; PMCID: PMC4565771
3. Suppa M, Daxhelet M, del Marmol V. Dépistage du mélanome [Melanoma secondary prevention]. *Rev Med Brux.* 2015 Sep;36(4):255-9. French. PMID: 26591309
4. Maire C, Vercambre-Darras S, Desmedt E. Diagnostic du mélanome [Diagnosis of melanoma]. *Rev Prat.* 2014 Jan;64(1):61-8. French. Erratum in: *Rev Prat.* 2014 Mar;64(3):349. PMID: 24649548
5. De Giorgi V, Papi F, Giorgi L, Savarese I, Verdelli A, Scarfì F, Gandini S. Skin self-examination and the ABCDE rule in the early diagnosis of melanoma: is the game over? *Br J Dermatol.* 2013 Jun;168(6):1370-1. doi: 10.1111/bjd.12250. PMID: 23738643
6. Garrido AQ, Wainstein AJA, Brandão MPA, de Vasconcellos Santos FA, Bittencourt FV, Ledsham C, Drummond-Lage AP. Diagnosis of Cutaneous Melanoma: the Gap Between the Knowledge of General Practitioners and Dermatologists in a Brazilian Population. *J Cancer Educ.* 2020 Aug;35(4):819-825. doi: 10.1007/s13187-020-01735-z. Erratum in: *J Cancer Educ.* 2020 May 27;; PMID: 32193871
7. Benelli C, Roscetti E, Dal Pozzo V. Reproducibility of the clinical criteria (ABCDE rule) and dermatoscopic features (7FFM) for the diagnosis of malignant melanoma. *Eur J Dermatol.* 2001 May-Jun;11(3):234-9. PMID: 11358731
8. Coups EJ, Manne SL, Stapleton JL, Tatum KL, Goydos JS. Skin self-examination behaviors among individuals diagnosed with melanoma. *Melanoma Res.* 2016 Feb;26(1):71-6. PMID: 26426762
9. Goldsmith SM, Solomon AR. A series of melanomas smaller than 4 mm and implications for the ABCDE rule. *J Eur Acad Dermatol Venereol.* 2007 Aug;21(7):929-34. doi: 10.1111/j.1468-3083.2006.02115.x. PMID: 17659002
10. Bandic J, Kovacevic S, Karabeg R, Lazarov A, Opric D. Teledermoscopy for Skin Cancer Prevention: a Comparative Study of Clinical and Teledermoscopic Diagnosis. *Acta Inform Med.* 2020 Mar;28(1):37-41. doi: 10.5455/aim.2020.28.37-41. PMID: 32210513; PMCID: PMC7085326

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